

Effects of land-use types on the abundance and diversity of avifauna on the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Habitat modification driven by population growth and development alters habitat conditions, leading to ecosystem imbalance and biodiversity loss. This study examined the influence of land-use types on avifaunal diversity within the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. Stratified random sampling divided the area into wooded, farmland, residential, and administrative zones, and bird species were surveyed using 500 m line transects. A total of 1,109 birds representing 59 species across 34 families were recorded, with the Laughing Dove (*Spilopelia senegalensis*) as the most abundant species. The highest proportion of individuals occurred in administrative areas (346; 31.19%), followed by residential (26.15%), farmland (23.81%), and wooded areas (18.85%). Farmland showed the highest species richness (41 species) and diversity (Shannon index = 3.02). Species similarity was highest between farmland and residential areas (0.61), and ten species (0.81%) were common across all land-use types, including *Spilopelia senegalensis*, *Lamprotornis pulcher*, *Halcyon senegalensis*, *Columba guinea*, *Pycnonotus barbatus*, *Bubalornis albirostris*, *Ptilostomus afer*, *Quelea quelea*, *Corythornis cristatus*, and *Centropus senegalensis*. Key nesting trees were *Faidherbia albida*, *Delonix regia*, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Syzygium cumini*, with nests constructed from twigs, bark strips, inflorescences, dry leaves, and grass. These findings highlight the importance of conserving habitat diversity to sustain bird populations and ecological balance, emphasizing the need to protect existing trees and promote planting of diverse native species across all land-use types.

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Introduction

Biodiversity is under threat due to human-induced changes in land use. While various aspects of biodiversity are increasingly studied in response to these changes, there is limited understanding of their effects on the abundance, richness, and diversity of avifauna in university campuses. Although bird species are distributed across the globe, habitat destruction and fragmentation have adversely affected their survival and distribution. Currently, scholars are debating the importance of habitat fragmentation and its impact on bird populations. Some researchers argue that habitat fragmentation is a major driver of population decline and extinction (Fahrig, 2003; Ewers & Didham, 2006), while others suggest that habitat quality and availability are more critical factors (Davis, 2003; Sekercioglu et al., 2015).

Biodiversity is under threat due to human-induced changes in land use. Human changes in natural habitats in the tropics, especially through land use alterations, pose a great threat to biodiversity (Turshak & Abdullahi, 2024). While various aspects of biodiversity are increasingly studied in response to these changes, there is limited understanding of their effects on the structure and composition of bird communities in university campuses. While various aspects of biodiversity are being increasingly studied in response to these changes, there remains a limited understanding of how they affect the structure and composition of bird communities on university campuses. The main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, provides a unique ecological environment for the study of birds' abundance, diversity, habitat preferences, and nesting behaviors. This campus features a variety of microhabitats, such as wooded areas, open fields, commercial, and urbanized zones. These varying habitats offer different levels of vegetation cover, food resources, and human interactions, which are known to influence bird distribution and nesting site selection (Seress & Liker, 2015). Diversity and species richness of birds are subject to the suitability of their habitats (Zara et al., 2021). Despite the avian population within the campus, the habitat preferences and nesting behaviors of many common bird species remain poorly documented. The interaction between natural habitat features and anthropogenic factors within the university setting creates a dynamic environment that can provide new insights into how birds utilize available resources for survival. Considering that the rates of urbanization are rising globally, the need to maintain and enhance urban biodiversity has become important (Afrifa et al., 2023). This study examines the relative influence of different land-use types as well as environmental resources on birds' diversity,

abundance, habitat preferences, and nesting materials within the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, thereby contributing to the broader understanding of avian ecology and informing conservation efforts in related regions.

This study is particularly relevant in light of growing evidence that urbanization creates both challenges and opportunities for bird populations. For example, urban areas can provide new nesting opportunities but also expose birds to risks such as reduced food availability, pollution, and predation (Stephens et al., 2004). By identifying and classifying the tree species used for nesting and examining the nesting materials employed, this research will provide actionable data to inform habitat restoration and urban planning efforts aimed at supporting avian biodiversity.

The outcomes of this research will contribute to broader fields of avian ecology and conservation biology, providing a foundation for future studies in related environments. Ultimately, it aims to promote biodiversity conservation while ensuring that the ecological and educational value of the university campus is preserved for future generations.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at Usmanu Danfodiyo University's main campus situated between latitude 13°6'0"N and 13°8'0"N and longitude 5°12'0"E and 5°16'0"E in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State. Sokoto State is located in the Sudan Savanna Zone in the extreme North-Western part of Nigeria between longitude 3°7'E and 6°5'E and latitude 11°6'N and 13°9'N. The vegetation of Sokoto is typical of the Sudan Savanna with intensive grass cover interspersed by a few trees and shrubs. The climate is semi-arid, characterized by low rainfall (Nigerian Meteorological Agency, 2017), a mean annual rainfall of 659mm, and relatively wide and rapid changes in temperature and humidity. The temperature is generally high. The highest mean monthly temperature is about 40-45°C in April, while the lowest mean monthly temperature occurs in December/January when the temperature could come down to 15°C (Zara et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Map showing the location of the trees supporting bird nests within the study area (Field Survey/UDUS GIS Lab, 2024)

Sampling Technique

The university campus was divided into four land-use types: wooded area, farmland, residential and commercial area, and administrative areas. A line transect approach was used within each habitat to survey bird populations. A Geographic Positioning System (GPS) was used to mark out the start and end points of each transect. Two (2) transects (500m), at an independent distance of 1 kilometer, were laid in each habitat due to accessibility. Transects were randomly laid along the existing routes within the study area, and bird observations were made along these transects. All counts were made in the mornings and evenings to capture temporal variations. Each transect was visited twice both in the morning (0700 hours – 0800 hours) and evening (0500 hours – 0600

hours) times, making a total of four visits per transect for a period of eight (8) weeks and all birds sighted were identified to species level, and recorded in a field notebook with the aid of binocular and field guide of West African Birds (Borrow & Demey, 2001). Twenty minutes were spent per transect to allow for better sighting of species. To avoid multiple counts of the same species, only birds within a radius of 50 meters from the transect line were recorded.

Materials and Equipment

The following are the materials used for conducting the survey;

1. A binocular
2. Survey datasheet
3. Geographic Positioning System (GPS)
4. Camera
5. Safety boot
6. A field guidebook of Birds of West Africa

Survey of Tree Species and Nesting Materials Used by Birds

To identify the tree species supporting bird nests and the materials used for nesting, a comprehensive survey was conducted across the four designated land-use types on the campus: wooded, farmland, residential and commercial areas, and administrative areas. Trees supporting bird nests were identified and recorded. Each nest was carefully examined to identify and record the materials used. This involved closely inspecting the nests for materials such as twigs, leaves, grass, and other plant parts. The materials were categorized based on their type and the specific bird species observed using them.

Taxonomic names

Handbook of the birds of the world and Birdlife International digital checklist of the birds of the world (2024) were used in naming the birds.

Data Analysis

The data obtained were subjected to descriptive statistics such as frequency distributions, percentages, and bar charts. Shannon-Weiner Diversity Index & Simpson's Index of Diversity were used to determine the diversity indices based on the land use types as illustrated below:

$$D = \frac{\sum n(n-1)}{N(N-1)} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, D = Simpson Index

n = Total number of individual species

N = Total number of all species

D ranges between 0 & 1. Hence, 1 represents infinite diversity, and 0 represents no diversity

$$SID = 1 - D \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where, SID = Simpson’s Index of Diversity

D = Simpson Index

$$H = -\sum(Pi \times \ln Pi) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where, H’ = Shannon-Weiner Diversity Index

Pi = Proportion of each individual (i.e. $\frac{ni}{N}$)

lnPi = Natural logarithm of the species proportion

When H’ is < 2, it indicates low diversity, 2 – 3.5 indicates moderate diversity, and ≥ 3.5 indicates high diversity.

The equitability index of evenness was used to determine evenness in the distribution of species in the different land use types.

$$E_H = \frac{H}{\ln(S)} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where, H = Shannon-Weiner Index

ln(S) = Natural logarithm of species richness

Sorenson similarity index was further used to validate the habitat preference as illustrated below:

$$SSI = \frac{2a}{2a+b+c} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where, SSI = Sorenson similarity index

a = Number of species the two land use types have in common

b = Total number of species found in land use type 1

c = Total number of species found in land use type 2

Relative frequency (RF) for individual species in the study area was calculated using the formula below;

$$\text{Relative frequency (RF)\%} = \frac{\text{Frequency of a species}}{\text{Total frequency of all specie}} \times 100$$

Results

Checklist of Avifauna in the study area

A total of 1,109 individuals were identified, representing 59 species across 34 groups. Columbidae was the highest represented family, with the Laughing Dove (*Spilopelia senegalensis*) alone accounting up 17.1% of the total birds. The study also recorded rare occurrences of families such as Nectariniidae (Beautiful Sunbird, *Cinnyris pulchellus*) and Dicruridae (Fork-tailed Drongo, *Dicrurus adsimilis*), each contributing only 0.54%. Results from the wooded area (Table 1) revealed that a total of 209 birds were documented, representing 38 species from 24 families. The variety of species in the wooded area indicates a broad species distribution, including uncommon sightings like the Grey-backed Camaroptera from the Cisticolidae family, which accounted for merely 0.54% of the birds' population in the study area. A total of 264 birds, representing 41 species spanning 23 families, were recorded in the farmland area. The Columbidae family remained predominant, with the Laughing Dove (*Spilopelia senegalensis*) accounting for 19.70% of the overall bird population in the farmland area. Table 1 illustrates bird variety in the residential area, where 290 individuals belonging to 31 species and 16 families were recorded, while the administrative area had the highest number of birds, with 346 individuals spanning 26 species and 13 families.

Avian Diversity and Similarity Indices

Table 1 highlights the presence of birds across different land-use types, with the administrative area ranking first in species abundance (346 birds), followed by the residential area (290 birds),

and the farmland area (264 birds), while the wooded area had the least species abundance (209 birds). However, when considering species richness, the farmland area ranked highest with 41 species, followed by the wooded area (38 species), and the residential area (31 species), while the administrative area (26 species) is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Checklist of avifauna in the study area

S/n	Scientific name	Common name	Family name	2024 IUCN Red List category	WA	FA	RA	AA	RF (%)
1	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>	Laughing Dove	Columbidae	LC	21	52	43	74	17.1
2	<i>Amadina fasciata</i>	Cut-throat finch	Estrildidae	LC	8	0	3	0	0.99
3	<i>Lamprotonis caudatus</i>	Long-tailed Glossy Starling	Sturnidae	LC	0	0	14	25	3.52
4	<i>Crithagra capistrata</i>	Black-faced Canary	Fringillidae	LC	6	2	0	0	0.72
5	<i>Ploceus heuglini</i>	Heuglin's Masked Weaver	Ploceidae	LC	9	0	0	0	0.81
6	<i>Vidua chalybeata</i>	Village Indigobird	Viduidae	LC	9	0	2	0	0.99
7	<i>Apus affinis</i>	Little swift	Apodidae	LC	0	0	2	0	0.18
8	<i>Turdoides plebejus</i>	Brown babbler	Leiotrichidae	LC	3	3	0	0	0.54
9	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	Village weaver	Ploceidae	LC	7	22	12	0	3.70
10	<i>Lagonosticta senegala</i>	Red-billed Firefinch	Estrildidae	LC	0	7	0	22	2.61
11	<i>Lamprotonis chalcurus</i>	Bronze-tailed Starling	Sturnidae	LC	0	21	23	6	4.51
12	<i>Tockus erythrorhynchus</i>	Red-billed Hornbill	Bucerotidae	LC	5	5	0	6	1.44
13	<i>Lagonosticta rufopicta</i>	Bar-breasted Firefinch	Estrildinae	LC	0	6	0	0	0.54
14	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle egret	Ardeidae	LC	0	0	16	0	1.44
15	<i>Dryoscopus gambensis</i>	Northern Puffback	Malaconotidae	LC	3	0	0	0	0.27
16	<i>Merops pusillus</i>	Little Bee-eater	Meropidae	LC	3	5	0	0	0.72
17	<i>Lanius corvinus</i>	Yellow-billed Shrike	Laniidae	LC	7	3	0	0	0.90
18	<i>Terpsiphone viridis</i>	African Paradise flycatcher	Monarchidae	LC	4	2	0	0	0.54
19	<i>Ploceus luteolus</i>	Little Weaver	Ploceidae	LC	0	10		5	1.35
20	<i>Melaenornis edolioides</i>	Northern Black flycatcher	Muscicapidae	LC	1	10	0	8	1.71
21	<i>Bubalornis albirostris</i>	White-billed Buffalo Weaver	Ploceidae	LC	3	1	12	59	6.76
22	<i>Lamprotonis pulcher</i>	Chestnut-bellied Starling	Sturnidae	LC	10	12	2	38	5.59
23	<i>Emberiza tahapisi</i>	Cinnamon-breasted Bunting	Emberizidae	LC	6	7	0	6	1.71
24	<i>Lamprotonis chalybaeus</i>	Greater Blue-eared Starling	Sturnidae	LC	2	6	0	5	1.17
25	<i>Corvus albus</i>	Pied crow	Emberizidae	NR	0	2	4	1	0.63
26	<i>Coracias abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Roller	Coraciidae	LC	3	0	2	0	0.45
27	<i>Cecropis senegalensis</i>	Mosque Swallow	Hirundinidae	LC	0	0	0	2	0.18
28	<i>Streptopelia decipiens</i>	Mourning Collared dove	Columbidae	LC	0	5	9	7	1.89
29	<i>Halcyon senegalensis</i>	Woodland Kingfisher	Alcedinidae	LC	3	1	5	2	0.99
30	<i>Ploceus vitellinus</i>	Vitelline Masked Weaver	Ploceidae	LC	0	5	0	0	0.45
31	<i>Anthus leucophrys</i>	plain-backed Pipit	Motacillidae	LC	6	2	14	0	1.98
32	<i>Sylvietta brachyura</i>	Northern crombec	Macrosphenidae	NR	0	5	0	0	0.45
33	<i>Prinia subflava</i>	Tawny flanked Prinia	Cisticolidae	LC	5	3	0	0	0.72
34	<i>Columba guinea</i>	Speckled Pigeon	Columbidae	LC	2	4	13	4	2.07
35	<i>Chalcomitra senegalensis</i>	Scarlet-chested Sunbird	Nectariniidae	LC	2	0	0	0	0.18
36	<i>Streptopelia vinacea</i>	Vinaceous Dove	Columbidae	LC	0	2	2	8	1.08
37	<i>Passer griseus</i>	Northern Grey headed Sparrow	Passeridae	LC	0	3	12	0	1.35
38	<i>Camaroptera brevicaudata</i>	Grey-backed Camaroptera	Cisticolidae	LC	6	0	0	0	0.54
39	<i>Ispidina picta</i>	African Pygmy kingfisher	Alcedinidae	LC	4	2	5	0	0.95
40	<i>Cinnyris pulchellus</i>	Beautiful sunbird	Nectariniidae	LC	0	1	0	0	0.09
41	<i>Agricola pallidus</i>	Pale Flycatcher	Muscicapidae	LC	5	0	2	9	1.44

42	<i>Euplectes franciscanus</i>	Northern Red Bishop	Ploceidae	LC	0	8	0	0	0.72
43	<i>Dendropicos obsoletus</i>	Brown-backed Woodpecker	Picidae	LC	3	0	0	0	0.27
44	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	Common Bulbul	Pycnonotidae	LC	7	8	24	14	4.78
45	<i>Phoeniculus somaliensis</i>	Blackwood hoopoe	Phoeniculidae	LC	4	2	0	0	0.54
46	<i>Ptilostomus afer</i>	Piapiac	Corvidae	LC	5	3	1	2	0.99
47	<i>Quelea quelea</i>	Red-billed Quelea	Ploceidae	LC	4	14	12	2	2.89
48	<i>Halcyon chelicuti</i>	Striped Kingfisher	Alcedinidae	LC	0	0	0	3	0.27
49	<i>Lamprotornis purpureus</i>	Purple Starling	Sturnidae	LC	7	0	5	15	2.43
50	<i>Glaucostreptopelia coeruleascens</i>	Lavender Waxbill	Estrildidae	LC	0	7	0	0	0.63
51	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	Fork-tailed Drongo	Dicruridae	LC	0	2	4	0	0.54
52	<i>Phoeniculus purpureus</i>	Green Woodhoopoe	Phoeniculidae	LC	2	2	1	0	0.45
53	<i>Corythornis cristatus</i>	Malachite Kingfisher	Alcedinidae	LC	4	3	7	2	1.44
54	<i>Galerida modesta</i>	Sun lark	Alaudidae	LC	0	6	7	0	1.17
55	<i>Uraeginthus bengalus</i>	Red-cheeked Cordon bleu	Estrildidae	LC	0	0	0	10	0.99
56	<i>Euodice cantans</i>	African Silverbill	Estrildidae	LC	5	0	0	6	0.95
57	<i>Centropus senegalensis</i>	Senegal Coucal	Cuculidae	LC	21	3	2	5	2.67
58	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	Helmeted Guineafowl	Numididae	LC	0	0	30	0	2.71
59	<i>Dendropicos goertae</i>	Grey Woodpecker	Picidae	LC	4	2	0	0	0.54
	Abundance				209	264	290	346	
	Species Richness				38	41	31	26	
S/n	Scientific name	Common name	Family name	2024 IUCN Red List category	WA	FA	RA	AA	RF (%)
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3	<i>Lamprotornis caudatus</i>	Long-tailed Glossy Starling	Sturnidae	LC	0	0	14	25	3.52
4	<i>Crithagra capistrata</i>	Black-faced Canary	Fringillidae	LC	6	2	0	0	0.72
5	<i>Ploceus heuglini</i>	Heuglin's Masked Weaver	Ploceidae	LC	9	0	0	0	0.81
6	<i>Vidua chalybeata</i>	Village Indigobird	Viduidae	LC	9	0	2	0	0.99
7	<i>Apus affinis</i>	Little swift	Apodidae	LC	0	0	2	0	0.18
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9	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	Village weaver	Ploceidae	LC	7	22	12	0	3.70
10	<i>Lagonosticta senegala</i>	Red-billed Firefinch	Estrildidae	LC	0	7	0	22	2.61
11	<i>Lamprotornis chalcurus</i>	Bronze-tailed Starling	Sturnidae	LC	0	21	23	6	4.51
12	<i>Tockus erythrorhynchus</i>	Red-billed Hornbill	Bucerotidae	LC	5	5	0	6	1.44
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51	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	Fork-tailed Drongo	Dicruridae	LC	0	2	4	0	0.54
52	<i>Phoeniculus purpureus</i>	Green Woodhoopoe	Phoeniculidae	LC	2	2	1	0	0.45
53	<i>Corythornis cristatus</i>	Malachite Kingfisher	Alcedinidae	LC	4	3	7	2	1.44
54	<i>Galerida modesta</i>	Sun lark	Alaudidae	LC	0	6	7	0	1.17
55	<i>Uraeginthus bengalus</i>	Red-cheeked Cordon bleu	Estrildidae	LC	0	0	0	10	0.99
56	<i>Euodice cantans</i>	African Silverbill	Estrildidae	LC	5	0	0	6	0.95
57	<i>Centropus senegalensis</i>	Senegal Coucal	Cuculidae	LC	21	3	2	5	2.67
58	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	Helmeted Guinea fowl	Numididae	LC	0	0	30	0	2.71
59	<i>Dendropicos goertae</i>	Grey Woodpecker	Picidae	LC	4	2	0	0	0.54
	Abundance				209	264	290	346	
	Species Richness				38	41	31	26	

Key: WA=Wooded Area, FA=Farmland Area, RA=Residential Area, AA=Administrative Area

LC=Last concern, NR=Not recognized

Taxonomic source= Handbook of the birds of the world and Birdlife International digital checklist of the birds of the world (2024)

The diversity results presented in Table 2 indicated that the residential area recorded the highest Simpson diversity index value of 0.93, the maximum observed value. This was followed by the farmland area (0.92), the wooded area (0.90), and the administrative area had the least (0.89). The Shannon-Weiner diversity index (Table 2) reflects moderate diversity levels, with the farmland area exhibiting the highest value of 3.02. This was followed by the residential area (2.83), the wooded area (2.65), and the administrative area had the least (2.60) Shannon diversity. Additionally, the equitability index values indicated a relatively higher evenness in the residential area, followed by the wooded area, the farmland area, and the administrative area. These diversity metrics were represented in Figures 1 and 2, showing the Simpson's Index of Diversity and Shannon-Weiner Index charts, respectively.

Table 2. Species diversity indices across the land use types in the study area

Land use type	D	SID	Richness	H'	E _H
Wooded	0.10	0.90	38	2.65	0.87
Farmland	0.08	0.92	41	3.02	0.86
Residential	0.07	0.93	31	2.83	0.88
Administrative	0.11	0.89	26	2.60	0.82

Key: D (Simpson Index), SID (Simpson Index of Diversity), H' (Shannon Diversity), E_H (Equitability Index)

Figure 2. Simpson's Index of Diversity Chart

Figure 3. Shannon-Weiner Index of Diversity Chart

Table 3 details the Sorensen similarity index, revealing that the farmland area and residential area exhibited the highest similarity (0.61), while the farmland and wooded areas demonstrated the

least similarity (0.39). This indicates a greater overlap in species composition between farmland and residential areas, likely due to shared ecological characteristics.

Table 3. Sorensen similarity between land uses

Land Use	Wooded	Farmland	Residential	Administrative
Wooded				
Farmland	0.39			
Residential	0.57	0.61		
Administrative	0.56	0.57	0.63	

Table 4 provides details on the tree species that supported the nests of various avifauna species, including their diameter at breast height (DBH) and canopy spread. Finally, Table 5 illustrates the nesting materials utilized by common avifauna species observed in the study area, emphasizing the variety of plant parts and species used for nest construction. These findings underscore the importance of specific tree species and plant materials in supporting avian nesting behaviors and maintaining bird populations in different land-use types.

Table 4. Trees supporting bird nests in the study area

Land Use	Tree Species	Family	DBH (cm)	Canopy Spread (m)
Administrative	<i>Delonix regia</i>	Fabaceae	100	11.99
Administrative	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Fabaceae	210	6.47
Administrative	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Fabaceae	270	22.22
Administrative	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Fabaceae	277	17.22
Residential	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Myrtaceae	130	12.14
Residential	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Myrtaceae	105	8.78
Farmland	<i>Balanite aegyptiaca</i>	Zygophyllaceae	209	8.33

Key: DBH (Diameter at Breast Height)

Table 5. Nesting materials used by avifauna in the study area

Avifauna	Plant Species Used	Parts Used
Village weaver	<i>Pennisetum pedicellatum</i>	Inflorescence & Leaves
	<i>Chloris virgata</i>	Inflorescence
	<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Inflorescence & Leaves
	<i>Panicum virgatum</i>	Inflorescence
	<i>Andropogon gayanus</i>	Leaves
White-billed buffalo weaver	<i>Senegalia senegal</i>	Twigs & Branches
	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Twigs & Branches
	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Twigs & Bark Strip
	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Dry leaves
Laughing dove	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	Dry grass blades & Stems

<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Twigs & Dry leaves
<i>Senegalia Senegal</i>	Twigs
<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i>	Dry grass blades & Stems
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Branches

Source: Field survey, 2024

Discussion

Influence of land-use types on avian diversity and abundance in the Study Area

The bird population and species richness observed in the study area reflect variations in habitat type, vegetation structure, and anthropogenic influence. The findings of this study also revealed that the study area still possesses significant conservation potential for urban birds. The administrative area recorded the highest species abundance (Table 1), which aligns with findings by Sekercioğlu et al. (2012), who noted that urban and administrative zones often support larger bird populations due to consistent food availability and fewer predators. However, farmland areas showed the highest species richness. This showed that farmland areas are essential for many bird species; it provides valuable and suitable habitat for the foraging and breeding activities of various kinds of bird species. On the other hand, the lower species richness observed in administrative areas compared to other land use types suggests that administrative areas may primarily attract generalist species adapted to human activities. This is in conformity with the findings of (Turshak & Abdullahi, 2024), who reported that the abundance of birds tends to reduce in transformed landscapes and is not suitable for birds seeking cover and food. Conversely, farmland areas supported the highest species richness, reflecting the structural heterogeneity provided by mixed vegetation, availability of food, and open spaces. This finding corroborates the study by Donald et al. (2001), which emphasized that agricultural landscapes with moderate human intervention often serve as biodiversity hotspots. This is also in tandem with Afrifa et al. (2023), who discovered that species richness was highest in farmland and abandoned farmland, while artificial mixed forests exhibited the highest number of unique species. The different building and construction activities ongoing in the study area and illegal cutting down of trees could lead to changes in the composition of the landscape, and may displace birds or alter or eliminate the conditions within a habitat that a species requires to survive. This could be one of the reasons for the low species richness recorded in administrative and residential areas in the study area. This is in tandem with Turshak and Abdullahi (2024), who observed that species such as Oriole Warblers that require vegetation cover

were observed to be confined to gallery forest where the vegetation cover was denser than savanna, whereas in sites of the logged and mining sites. Biodiversity plays a crucial role in maintaining the balance of both human and natural environments, providing essential ecosystem services (Hooper et al., 2005). However, escalating human activities are causing severe biodiversity crises (Newbold et al., 2015), with land use change being a primary driver of global biodiversity loss (Rurangwa et al., 2021).

The results of this study suggest that higher bird diversity is found in Residential areas, perhaps due to habitat complexity, which can be attributed to the variety of ornamental plants, tree cover, and food resources available in urban gardens. This is contrary to Afrifa et al. (2022), who reported that species diversity indicators decreased significantly with increasing land-use intensity. The findings of this study also is in disagreement with Mugatha et al. (2024), who reported that species richness and diversity typically decline as land use changes from natural to disturbed. The wooded area, while hosting fewer birds, had a notable Simpson diversity index (0.90). This suggests that wooded habitats, despite their limited size, provide essential nesting and foraging opportunities for certain specialist species, a pattern highlighted in the work of Fuller et al. (2007).

The Shannon-Weiner diversity index (Figure 3) recorded in farmland indicates moderate diversity (Table 2), aligning with findings by Tschardt et al. (2012), who reported that traditional agricultural systems often balance species richness and abundance. Although less than 1% of the world's bird species prefer agricultural areas as their primary habitat, nearly a third of all bird species use such habitats occasionally (Sekercioglu et al., 2012). However, the relatively low equitability index in the administrative area points to an uneven distribution of bird species, possibly due to dominance by a few highly adaptable species such as *Spilopelia senegalensis* (Laughing Dove) and *Bubalornis albirostris* (White-billed Buffalo Weaver), and human development activities. Biodiversity plays a crucial role in maintaining the balance of both human and natural environments, providing essential ecosystem services (Hooper et al., 2005). However, escalating human activities are causing severe biodiversity crises (Newbold et al., 2015), with land use change being a primary driver of global biodiversity loss (Rurangwa et al., 2021). This change involves altering the physical environment and vegetation structure at the habitat level, leading to unpredictable fluctuations in biodiversity (Si et al., 2017) and continuous changes in biological structure and ecological community composition (Hooper et al., 2005), with implications for different dimensions of biodiversity, such as taxonomic diversity, functional diversity, and

phylogenetic diversity. The Sorensen similarity index highlights an overlap in species composition between farmland and residential areas. This could be attributed to the shared use of nesting materials and food resources, as noted by Naeem et al. (1994), who emphasized functional redundancy in ecosystems (Table 3).

The use of specific tree species for nesting, as shown in Tables 4 and 5, emphasizes the important role of vegetation in supporting avian species. Species like *Delonix regia* and *Faidherbia albida* provided structural support for nests to most of the avian species in the study area, reflecting their ecological value in urban and farmland settings. The nesting materials documented in Table 5 further reveal habitat-specific adaptations. For example, village weavers' reliance on grass inflorescence and laughing doves' preference for twigs highlight the relationship between bird species and vegetation availability, consistent with studies by Collias & Collias (1984). The implications of these findings are significant for conservation and land management. High bird diversity in residential and farmland areas suggests that maintaining habitat heterogeneity in human-dominated landscapes can support biodiversity. However, the dominance of a few species in administrative areas indicates a need for enhanced vegetation diversity to support less adaptable species. Moreover, the relatively low diversity and richness in wooded areas emphasize the importance of preserving natural habitats to sustain specialist species.

Conclusion

This study sheds more light on the important role of habitat diversity and vegetation structure in shaping the distribution, species richness, and nesting behavior of common bird species within the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria. Farmlands and residential areas emerged as key habitats for supporting species richness and diversity, while wooded areas and administrative zones contributed unique ecological benefits for certain specialist and generalist species. The preferences for specific tree species and nesting materials emphasize the critical interdependence between avian populations and their habitats, emphasizing the need for preserving and enhancing vegetation cover and diversity. These findings provide necessary information on the habitat preferences and resource utilization of birds in a semi-arid environment, contributing to the broader understanding of avian ecology in human-modified landscapes. By integrating these insights into campus management and conservation strategies, the ecological integrity of the campus can be maintained, ensuring that it continues to serve as a refuge for avian biodiversity in the region. This research serves as a foundation for future studies on habitat and resource dynamics

in similar ecological settings. As a whole, the most commonly encountered species among the four (4) land-use types were: Chestnut-bellied Starling (*Lamprotornis pulcher*), Common bulbul (*Pycnonotus barbatus*), Woodland Kingfisher (*Halcyon senegalensis*), White-billed Buffalo weaver (*Bubalornis albirostris*), and Laughing Dove (*Spilopelia senegalensis*). These birds are mostly associated with human communities, and some are generalist feeders. Their characteristics allow them to easily adapt to their environments, so they are at lower risk of extinction

Recommendations

1. Efforts should be made to preserve existing trees, particularly those identified as critical for nesting, such as *Delonix regia*, *Faidherbia albida*, and *Syzygium cumini*. This can enhance habitat complexity and support a broader range of bird species.
2. Habitat-specific management practices should be adopted to maintain the ecological integrity of different zones. In farmlands, agricultural activities should integrate agroforestry practices to balance human use with biodiversity conservation. For residential and administrative areas, landscaping with bird-friendly plants and maintaining green corridors can support species diversity and movement.
3. The wooded areas should be protected from degradation and encroachment through designated conservation strategies within the campus.
4. Awareness programs for students, staff, and the local community should be conducted by the University authority to enlighten the public on the ecological importance of birds and their habitats. Encouraging participation in conservation activities can foster a sense of environmental stewardship.
5. Regular monitoring of bird populations and habitats should be conducted to track changes in species richness, abundance, and diversity.
6. Further studies on seasonal variations in bird activity and the impact of environmental changes on nesting behaviour can provide a deeper understanding of the behaviour of birds in the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

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